

Using OpenStreetMap with R :: CHEATSHEET

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is an open and collaborative spatial database that provides geographical features on a global scale. This cheatsheet identifies a list of R packages dedicated to its processing.

600 Peachtree Street
NE, Atlanta

Geocoding

`{tidygeocoder}`: Forward and reverse geocoding. The package interfaces the Nominatim API, that uses OpenStreetMap to find locations by name and address.

```
geo(address, method = "osm") # retrieve X/Y from address  
reverse_geo(lat, lon) # retrieve address from X/Y
```

`{tidygeocoder}` uses a Nominatim demo server by default but many other geocoding services can be used.

Interact with OSM database

`{osmapiR}`: Fetch and save data from / to OSM database. This package is mainly used for editing or exploring metadata.

```
osm_bbox_objects(bbox) # retrieve data by bounding box  
osm_history_object(osm_type, osm_id) # object history  
osm_query_changeset(bbox, user, time) # query changeset
```

This package interfaces the OSM API.

Download OSM tiles

`{maptiles}`: Create map using tiles from different providers. Most providers use OpenStreetMap to build their tiles.

Alternatives: `{rosm}`, `{OpenStreetMap}`

```
get_tiles(x, provider, zoom) # download raster tiles  
get_credit(provider) # get the attribution of map tiles
```

The tiles use the `SpatRaster` format from `{terra}`.

Import & extract OSM data

`{osmextract}`: Download data at planet, country or regional scale. Adapted for large datasets
`{osmdata}`: Download data in a bounding box or a polygon. Adapted for specific use on smaller areas

```
osmextract::oe_get(place, layer, provider) # download OSM data from an administrative region  
  
osmdata::opq(bbox, osm_types) |> # build an Overpass query  
add_osm_feature(key, value) |> # add a feature to the query  
osmdata_sf() # send the query and return an sf object
```

`{osmdata}` accesses OSM data via the read-only Overpass API.

Routing

`{osrm}` and `{valh}`: Interfaces between R and OSM-based routing services **OSRM** and **Valhalla**. Used to compute routes, trips, isochrones and travel distances matrices (travel time and kilometric distances), allowing different profiles (foot, car, bike).

Alternatives: `{r5r}`, `{opentripplanner}`, `{openrouteservice}`

```
osrmRoute / vl_route() # get shortest path between two points  
osrmTable / vl_matrix() # get travel time matrix between points  
osrmTrip / vl_optimized_route() # get shortest optimized routes between multiple points  
osrmIsochrone / vl_isochrone() # get polygons of isochrones  
osrmNearest / vl_locate() # get the nearest point on the street network
```

Both these packages use demo servers. For intensive use, it is recommended to use your own server.

Mapping

Downloaded layers can be mapped with any cartographic backend such as `{mapsf}`, `{tmap}` or `{ggplot2}`, for vector and raster format. Do not forget the credits: © OpenStreetMap Contributors

This cheatsheet presents an **opiniated** and **non exhaustive** list of OSM related packages. OSM data are redistributed under ODbL licence. You are free to: **share**, **create** and **adapt** as long as you: **attribute**, **share-alike** and **keep open**. Some of these packages use demo server for their example. Please check **API policies** and **restrictions** before querying them.

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Geocoding - Find coordinates from points

The `geo()` function retrieves coordinates from a point. Otherwise, the `reverse_geo()` function gives an address from X/Y coordinates. Use the `method` argument to choose a specific geocoding service.

```
library(sf) # for spatial data processing
library(tidygeocoder)
# An address in Batman
pt <- geo(address = "29 Ahmet Arif Bulvarı, Batman, Türkiye",
          method = "osm") # use Nominatim API
# Transform dataframe with X/Y coords to an sf object
(pt <- st_as_sf(pt, coords = c("long", "lat"), crs = 4326))
```

```
Simple feature collection with 1 feature and 1 field
Geometry type: POINT
Dimension:      XY
Bounding box:  xmin: 41.13342 ymin: 37.88794 xmax: 41.13342 ymax: 37.88794
Geodetic CRS:  WGS 84
# A tibble: 1 × 2
  address                                geometry
* <chr>                                <POINT [°]>
1 29 Ahmet Arif Bulvarı, Batman, Türkiye (41.13342 37.88794)
```

Extract OSM tiles - Raster format

The `get_tiles()` function retrieves tiles based on a spatial object extent. Use the `zoom` argument to define a zoom level. Use the `provider` argument to choose a specific map server.

```
library(maptiles)
# Define a bounding box around our address
bbox <- st_bbox(st_buffer(pt, 500))
# Download tiles covering the bounding box
tiles <- get_tiles(x = bbox, project = FALSE,
                  provider = "CartoDB.Positron",
                  zoom = 16, crop = TRUE)
```

Download OSM objects - from Overpass API

Combine `opq()`, `add_osm_feature()` and `osmdata_sf()` functions to select a spatial extent in which to query the API, and return an `{sf}` object. Here an example with **post offices**.

```
library(osmdata)
# Select our bounding box
q <- opq(bbox = bbox, osm_types = "node") # only points
# Add post offices to the query
req <- add_osm_feature(opq = q, key = 'amenity',
                      value = "post_office")
# Launch query and return an sf object
poi <- osmdata_sf(req)
poi <- poi$osm_points
```

Get metadata of OSM objects

```
library(osmapiR)
# Get information on a post office
hosm <- osm_history_object(osm_id = poi[[2, "osm_id"]])
nrow(hosm) # number of changes
```

```
[1] 7
hosm$timestamp[3] # date of the last change
```

```
[1] "2019-05-30 09:30:42 GMT"
```

```
unique(hosm$uid) # IDs of contributors
```

```
[1] "1386706" "9231066"
```

```
osm_get_user_details("1386706")["account_created"] # details
```

```
account_created
1 2013-04-24 10:51:47
```

Download OSM objects - from a provider

Different providers are available with the `oe_providers()` function.

The `oe_get()` is an all-in-one function that matches a place with an OSM extract, downloads it, and converts it to the `{sf}` format.

Be careful, the following code downloads OSM for whole Turkey (605 MB).

```
library(osmextract)
osm_pt <- oe_get(place = "Turkey", layer = "points",
                extra_tags = "amenity")
# Extract hospitals
osm_pt <- osm_pt[osm_pt$amenity %in% c("hospital"), ]
```

Routing - interface OSRM and Valhalla APIs

You can define the transport mode with arguments `osrm.profile` for `{osrm}` or `costing` for `{valh}`.

```
library(osrm)
library(valh)
# Shortest route from the address to the first post office
road_o <- osrmRoute(src = pt, dst = poi[[1, ],
                  osrm.profile = "bike")
road_v <- vl_route(src = pt, dst = poi[[1, ],
                  costing = "bicycle")
# Durations in minutes
(durations <- list(osrm = road_o$duration,
                  valh = road_v$duration))
```

```
$osrm
[1] 2.726667
$valh
[1] 2.3138
```

Map the results

Objects from OSM are of class `SpatRaster` or `sf`, they can be mapped with any cartographic backend.

```
library(mapsf)
road_o <- st_transform(road_o, 3857)
road_v <- st_transform(road_v, 3857)
pt <- st_transform(pt, 3857)
po <- st_transform(poi[[1, ], 3857)
mf_raster(tiles)
mf_map(road_o, col = "darkblue", lwd = 4, add = TRUE)
mf_map(road_v, col = "darkred", lwd = 4, add = TRUE)
mf_map(pt, col = "darkgreen", cex = 3, add = TRUE)
mf_map(po, col = "gold1", cex = 3, add = TRUE)
mf_title("A Postman in Batman")
mf_scale(100, scale_units = "m")
mf_credits(txt = "@ OpenStreetMap contributors @ CARTO")
mf_legend(type = "typo_line", val = c("OSRM", "Valhalla"),
          pal = c("darkblue", "darkred"), pos = "topright",
          lwd = 4, val_cex = .8, title = NA)
mf_text(x = pt, txt = "Home", pos = "bottom", offset = 2)
mf_text(x = po, txt = "Post\nOffice", pos = "topright")
```

